

FEATURES OF THE APPLICATION OF COMBAT TECHNIQUES IN VARIOUS SITUATIONS BY INTERNAL AFFAIRS OFFICERS: EXPERIENCE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The article examines the issues of professional and applied training for cadets of educational institutions. It focuses on modeling the apprehension of offenders on an obstacle course using combat techniques.

Keywords: Physical and combat training, obstacle course, modeling, situation, honor, dignity, combat techniques.

The large-scale reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan today are taking place within the framework of the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy, which represents a comprehensive action plan for modernizing the economy, improving social security, enhancing the quality of education and healthcare, as well as protecting the nation's cultural and spiritual heritage. In recent years, measures have been implemented in the system of internal affairs bodies to radically improve their activities in the field of public safety. A unified system for managing existing forces and resources has been introduced, with a clear division of responsibilities with the National Guard for maintaining public order on streets and in public places. In turn, to increase the efficiency of service activities, modern information and communication systems have been implemented for remote management of all units and patrols.

To address the challenges facing internal affairs bodies at the present stage, it is necessary to establish a mobile, flexible, and highly professional system for detecting, preventing, and suppressing violations and crimes. This system should be based on the use of the most advanced forms, methods, and means of ensuring public safety, maintaining public order, preventing violations, conducting operational-search activities, and carrying out investigative actions.

In this context, staffing internal affairs bodies with highly qualified specialists who have undergone comprehensive professional training is of paramount importance. There is a need to significantly improve the system of spiritual and moral education, training, retraining, and professional development of employees, as well as to review the order of service and material and technical support for the activities of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs has established a system of full-time and part-time training in 8 fields. To form the personnel core from an early age, 14 departmental academic lyceums, "Temurbeklar maktabi," and a specialized boarding school have been created.

Improving the system of educational institutions within internal affairs bodies implies a fundamental and comprehensive enhancement of the professional training and upbringing

of future internal affairs officers. The goal is to develop patriotic and people-oriented representatives of the state with high spiritual and moral qualities, faithful to their duty, based on the principle of "For the honor and dignity of man."

In this regard, one of the main requirements for the professional activities of internal affairs officers is to increase the level of combat, physical, and psychological training of personnel in accordance with modern forms and methods of combating crime.

According to the training program of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the subject "Physical and Combat Training" on the topic: "Actions to Detain a Violator in the All-Army Obstacle Course," the cadets study the technique of performing individual combat tactics. Practical classes on the obstacle course are conducted in camouflage mode. Practical classes in other sections of the curriculum are held in a sporting form. Two obstacles were chosen to simulate the detention of the offender in the obstacle strip: a wall and a damaged bridge with a height of 2 meters. During the practical exercises on detention of the offender in the common troop obstacle strip, the following means of combat techniques were used:

- special preparatory exercises for the wrestler: insurance, skating and falling on the right, left side; toppling: forward, backward, through the right, left shoulder, through the partner, comprehensive exercises for agility;

- combat stations: frontal, left-right. Movements in combat stations. Performing defensive-attacking actions - striking with the hands: straight, sideways, below, from above, on the back; striking with the feet: straight, to the side; protection with the supports of the forearms: up, down, to the side, inside, outside, protection with the supports of both forearms;

- detention and accompaniment techniques: hands behind the back "push," "ribble," "hike," "lock"; hand lever inside and outside;

- standing techniques: throws over the hips, over the back, with two legs in front and back, front and rear tread, slices;

- protection-attacking actions against knife attacks: from above, from the side to the neck, from the side to the body, from below to the stomach, upside down, straight;

- defensive-attacking actions against the threat of firearms (pistols): front to the support, back to the support;

- defense-attacking actions against the threat of firearms (automatic weapons);

- defensive-attacking actions against attempts to disarm (arms in the housing): when the enemy attacks from the front, back, and side.

Combat tactics complexes can be performed both with and without weapons, as well as using various sambo combat techniques.

Law-breaker protection, detention and escort

Picture. 1

Picture. 2

Picture. 3

Picture. 4

Rear foot protection, detention and escort

Picture. 1

Picture. 2

Picture. 3

Picture. 4

Rear foot protection, detention and escort

Picture. 1

Picture. 2

Picture. 3

Picture. 4

Picture. 5

Picture. 6

Knife protection, detention and escort

Picture. 1

Picture. 2

Picture. 3

Picture. 4

Picture. 5

Picture. 6

In a number of areas of physical training, including obstacle handling, there is a need for high automation not only of individual motor skills, but also of their various combinations. This is explained by the fact that successful actions in extreme situations require the ability to instantly switch from one method to another, while acting quickly and effectively. Therefore, in obstacle course lessons, it is not enough to master the technique of individual techniques that are part of the obstacle course exercises and bring their execution to automatism, it is also necessary to develop a high ability to instantly switch from one type of activity to another.

Therefore, the "Action on Detention of Offenders in the All-Army Obstacles Belt" using combat methods will allow for a higher level of training for cadets of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and will contribute to the effective application of combat methods in the performance of operational and service tasks.

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